

Terpenoids: Part LXXXV. Claisen Rearrangement involving Furan Ring System. Synthesis of Rosefuran and Sesquirosefuran

O. P. VIG, A. K. VIG, V. K. HANDA and S. D. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh

Manuscript received 8 April 1974; accepted 1 August 1974

Claisen rearrangement of the vinyl ether from 3-furylmethanol provides the aldehyde, 3-methyl-2(ethanol) furan, in good yield. This aldehyde has been used for the synthesis of rosefuran as well as sesquirosefuran.

FOR the synthesis of terpenoids through Wittig olefination, the preparation of suitable aldehydes or ketones is a vital step. A general synthetic route for this purpose is the Claisen rearrangement of appropriate allyl vinyl ethers. Several reports in this direction have already appeared from this laboratory¹⁻⁵ and elsewhere^{6,7}.

Fascinated by the findings of Thomas and Ozainne⁸ that a double bond in the furan ring can be induced to participate in a Claisen-cope type rearrangement, we set out to investigate in detail the Claisen rearrangement reaction involving furan ring double bond.

With the intention of accomplishing the synthesis of the title compounds, we prepared⁹ 3-furylmethanol (III) as our starting material. Conversion of (III) to the allyl vinyl ether (IV) was achieved by mercuric acetate catalysed transesterification using ethyl vinyl ether¹⁰. Pyrolysis of (IV) in a sealed tube under nitrogen gave the aldehyde (V) in about 80 per cent yield. The structure of this aldehyde was

confirmed through elemental analysis and the characteristic IR absorption bands at 2720 cm^{-1} (aldehyde, C-H), 1720 cm^{-1} (aldehyde, C=O), and 875, 790, 725 cm^{-1} (furan ring). It may be noted here that the originally formed unstable structure after Claisen rearrangement gets converted into the stable furan ring system through a 1,3-hydrogen shift (cf. 8).

Rosefuran (I) and sesquirosefuran (II) have been isolated^{11,12} from natural oils and their structures confirmed through chemical as well as spectral evidences. Further confirmation regarding these structures came from their synthesis which were recently published by two different schools^{11,13} utilizing a similar approach. We describe in this

communication new synthesis of these furanoid terpenes using a common intermediate. This intermediate is the aldehyde (V) whose preparation we have just described.

The aldehyde (V) was subjected to Wittig reaction with isopropylidene-triphenylphosphorane to furnish almost quantitatively rosefuran (I). The structure of this product was established through the comparison of IR spectrum with that of the natural product¹¹.

Grignard reaction with isopropenyl magnesium bromide on (V) provided the allyl alcohol (VI) which was converted as usual into the vinyl ether (VII). Claisen migration of (VII) furnished 60% of the aldehyde (VIII). Finally the aldehyde (VIII) upon Wittig reaction with isopropylidene-triphenylphosphorane gave sesquirosefuran (II) in high yield. The IR spectrum of (II) was found exactly identical with that reported in the literature.¹²

Experimental

B.P.s are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Infrared spectrophotometer with sodium chloride optics using thin liquid films.

3-Vinyloxymethylfuran(IV) :

3-Furylmethanol (III, 10 g) was mixed with ethyl vinyl ether (80 ml) and freshly crystallized mercuric acetate (1 g) and the mixture heated under gentle reflux for 10 hr. The contents were chilled in ice and mixed with sodium carbonate solution and stirred for 30 min. The organic layer was separated, washed with water and dried (K_2CO_3). Evaporation of the solvent and chromatography of the residue on alumina furnished on elution with petroleum ether (40°–60°), the vinyl ether (IV) which was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure to afford (IV, 7.5 g, 60%); b.p. 65°–70°/10–12 mm; ν_{max} 3100, 2940, 1620, 1400, 1295, 1200, 1060, 885, 790 and 730 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 67.54; H, 6.74; $C_7H_8O_2$ requires : C, 67.73; H, 6.56%).

3-Methyl-2(ethanol)furan(V) :

The vinyl ether (IV, 7 g) was heated for 35 min. under nitrogen in a fully immersed, half filled sealed tube in an oil-bath at 160°. Direct distillation provided 6 g (85%) of the aldehyde (V); b.p. 70°–75°/10–12 mm; ν_{max} 2940, 2720, 1720, 1625, 1500, 1450, 1400, 1355, 880, 790 and 740 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 67.56; H, 6.48; $C_7H_8O_2$ requires : C, 67.73; H, 6.56%). 2,4-DNP of (V) melted at 118°–20° (ethanol). (Found : N, 18.36, $C_{13}H_{12}N_4O_5$ requires : N, 18.42%).

3-Methyl-2(3-methylbutenyl-2)furan(I) :

To the isopropylidetriphenylphosphorane, prepared from sodium hydride (0.720 g; 50%) in dimethyl sulphoxide (7.5 ml) and isopropyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (6.67 g) in dimethylsulphoxide (15 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere, was added the aldehyde (V, 1.28 g) in THF (5 ml) with occasional shaking. The contents were stirred for 3 hr and left overnight. The reaction mixture was poured into cold water and worked out in the usual manner to obtain rosefuran (I; 1 g); b.p. 60°–65°/9–10 mm; yield (67%). (Found : C, 79.65; H, 9.50; $C_{10}H_{14}O$ requires : C, 79.95; H, 9.39%). ν_{max} 2950, 1675, 1625, 1505, 1460, 1380, 1510, 1460, 1380, 1160, 1090, 900, 865 and 730 cm^{-1} .

3-Methyl-2(2-hydroxy-3-methyl-3-butenyl)furan(VI) :

Grignard reagent was prepared to the exclusion of moisture from dry magnesium turnings (3 g), isopropenyl bromide (15 g) in anhydrous THF (200 ml). This was cooled in ice-cold water and the aldehyde (V; 6.4 g) in THF (20 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring during a period of 30 min. After the addition was complete, the contents were left overnight at room temperature and thereafter the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for about an hour. The cooled contents were decomposed with saturated solution in NH_4Cl . The organic layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted with ether. The total extract was dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent was removed. The residue was distilled under reduced pressure to obtain (VI) as a yellow oil, b.p. 85°–90°/7–10 mm; yield 5.8 g (63.8%). ν_{max} 3450, 2940, 1625, 1450, 1400, 1350,

960, 910, 885, 784, and 730 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 71.98; H, 8.58; $C_{10}H_{14}O_2$ requires : C, 72.26; H, 8.49%).

3-Methyl-2(2-vinyloxy-3-methyl-3-butenyl)furan(VII) :

The allylic alcohol (VI, 5 g) was mixed with allyl vinyl ether (40 ml) and freshly crystallized mercuric acetate (800 mg) and the mixture heated under reflux for 16 hr. The contents were chilled in ice and mixed with sodium carbonate solution and stirred for 30 min. The organic layer was separated and dried (K_2CO_3). Evaporation of the solvent and chromatography of the residue on neutral alumina furnished on elution with pet. ether (40°–60°), the vinyl ether (VII) which was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure to afford (VII; 3.4 g; 62%); b.p. 80°–85°/7–10 mm. ν_{max} 3100, 2940, 1645, 1620, 1500, 1450, 1350, 1200, 960, 910, 885, 790 and 730 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 74.68; H, 8.48; $C_{12}H_{16}O_2$ requires : C, 74.97; H, 8.39%).

3-Methyl-2(3-methyl-2-en-6-hexenal)furan(VIII) :

Vinyl ether (VII, 3 g) was heated for 25 min., under nitrogen, in a fully immersed half filled sealed tube in an oil bath at 180°. After cooling, the product was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish (VIII, 2.68 g; 86%); b.p. 95°–98°/10–12 mm. ν_{max} 2940, 2730, 1720, 1610, 1500, 1460, 1385, 960, 885, 785 and 740 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 74.64; H, 8.58; $C_{12}H_{16}O_2$ requires : C, 74.97; H, 8.39%).

3-Methyl-2(3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadienyl)furan(II) :

Sodium hydride (720 mg; 50%) was washed three times with *n*-hexane and blown dry with nitrogen. Dry DMSO (7.5 ml) was added and the mixture was stirred vigorously under nitrogen at 65° until hydrogen evolution ceased (45 min.). The light green solution was cooled to room temperature and a solution of 6.67 g of isopropyltriphenylphosphonium iodide in 15 ml of DMSO was rapidly added. To the deep red solution was added the aldehyde (VIII, 1.92 g) in THF (6 ml). The contents were stirred and left overnight at room temperature and then were poured in iced water and worked up in the usual manner to obtain the crude product. This was chromatographed over neutral alumina, when elution with pet. ether (40°–60°) gave the sesquirosefuran (II) which was further purified by distillation under vacuum, b.p. 101°–102°/10–12 mm; yield 1.6 g (69%). (Found : C, 82.67; H, 10.08; $C_{15}H_{22}O$ requires : C, 82.51; H, 10.16%). ν_{max} 2940, 1620, 1500, 1450, 1385, 1160, 1140, 1080, 1020, 960, 880, 790 and 735 cm^{-1} , which was identical with that published in the literature¹².

References

1. O. P. VIG, S. D. SHARMA and INDER RAJ, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, 4, 127.
2. O. P. VIG, S. D. SHARMA, SURESH CHANDER and INDER RAJ, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 538.
3. O. P. VIG, J. C. KAPOOR and S. D. SHARMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 541.

4. O. P. VIG, J. C. KAPOOR, (Miss) J. PURI and S. D. SHARMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 6, 60.
5. O. P. VIG, A. K. VIG, V. K. HANDA and S. D. SHARMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, (in press).
6. (a) G. SAUCY and R. MARBET, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1967, 50, 2091.
(b) R. MARBET and G. SAUCY, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1967, 50, 2095.
7. K. C. BRANNOCK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 3379.
8. A. F. THOMAS and M. OZAINNE, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1970, 220.
9. E. SHERMAN and E. D. AMSTUTZ, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2195.
10. R. F. CHURCH, R. E. IRELAND and J. A. MARSHALL, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, 31, 2526.
11. G. BUCHI, E. KOVATS, P. ENGISST and G. UHDE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, 33, 1227.
12. N. HAYASHI, H. KOMAE, S. EGUCHI, M. NAKAYAMA, S. HAYASHI and T. SAKAO, *Chemistry and Industry*, 1972, 572.
13. Y. GOPICHAND, R. S. PRASAD and K. K. CHAKRAVARTI, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1973, 5177.